

Oscillation Theorems for Third Order Nonlinear Delay Differential Equation with “Maxima”

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Abstract. In this paper we obtain oscillation criteria for the third order delay differential equation with “maxima” of the form

$$\left(a(t)\left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)\right)^\beta\right) + q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) = 0, \quad t \geq t_0$$

via comparison with the oscillatory behavior of first order differential equations. Some examples are given to illustrate the main results.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 34C10, 34K11

Keywords and Phrases: Oscillation; third order; differential equation with “maxima”.

1.Introduction

This paper deals with the oscillation of third order nonlinear delay differential equation with maxima of the form

$$(1.1) \quad \left(a(t)\left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)\right)^\beta\right) + q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) = 0, \quad t \geq t_0,$$

subject to the following conditio

(H1) $a(t), b(t)$ and $q(t) \in C([t_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$;

(H2) α, β and γ are quotient of odd positive integer;

(H3) $\sigma(t) \in C^1([t_0, \infty), \mathbf{R})$, $\sigma(t) \leq t$ for $t \geq t_0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(t) = \infty$;

By a solution of equation (1.1), we mean a function $x(t)$ defined for all $t \geq t_x \geq t_0$ such that $x(t), b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha$, $a(t)\left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)\right)^\beta$ are continuous and differentiable for all $t \geq t_x$ and satisfies equation (1.1) for all $t \geq t_x$ and satisfy $\sup\{|x(t)|: t \geq T\} > 0$ for any $T \geq t_x$. It will be assumed that equation (1.1) has nontrivial solutions exist for all $t_0 \geq 0$. A solution of equation (1.1) is called oscillatory if it has infinitely many zeros, otherwise it is called nonoscillatory.

In the last few years, the oscillation and asymptotic behavior of differential equations with “maxima” received considerable attention because of the fact that they appear in the study of systems with automatic regulation, and automatic control of various technical systems. It often occurs that the law of regulation depends on maximum values of some regulated state parameter over certain intervals, see [4, 9].

In [1, 2, 3, 5], the authors study the oscillatory behavior of solutions of equation (1.1) when $\alpha = 1$ or

$\beta = 1$, and therefore in this paper we consider equation (1.1) which include many results considered in [1, 2, 3, 5] as special cases.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the oscillatory behavior of solutions of equation (1.1) with the cases

$$(1.2) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} dt = \infty, \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} dt = \infty$$

and

$$(1.3) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} dt < \infty, \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} dt < \infty.$$

The results obtained in this paper improvement and extend that of in [1, 2, 3, 5], and many known results.

3. Oscillation Results

In this section, we state and prove our main results. Without loss of generality, we consider only positive solutions of equation (1.1) since the proof for the negative solution is similar. We begin with the following lemmas which will play an important role in proving the main results. Define

$$B(t, t_0) = \int_{t_0}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds,$$

$$A_1(t) = \int_t^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds,$$

$$A_2(t) = \int_t^{\infty} \frac{1}{a^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds.$$

Lemma 2.1 *Let there is a $T_1 \geq t_0$ such that $\sigma(t) > T_1$ for $t \geq T > T_1$ and*

(C₁) either

$$(2.1) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} dt = \infty,$$

or

$$(2.2) \quad \int_T^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(t)} \left(\int_T^t q(s) A_2^\gamma(s) B^\gamma(s, T) ds \right)^{1/\beta} dt = \infty$$

(C₂) either

$$(2.3) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} dt = \infty$$

or

$$(2.4) \quad \int_T^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\int_T^t \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_T^s q(u) A_1^\gamma(\sigma(u)) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha} dt = \infty$$

hold. If x be an eventually positive solution of equation (1.1), then x satisfies one of the following two cases:

(I) $x'(t) > 0, (b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) > 0$ for all $t \geq T$;

(II) $x'(t) < 0, (b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) > 0$ for all $t \geq T$.

Proof. Let $x(\sigma(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1 \geq t_0$. From equation (1.1), we have

$$\left(a(t) \left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)^\beta \right) \right)' = -q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) < 0 \text{ for all } t \geq t_1.$$

Then $a(t)(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)^\beta$ strictly decreasing for all $t \geq t_1$ and thus $x'(t)$ and $b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha$ are eventually of one sign. We show that $b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$. Now assume $b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha \leq 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$ and we have two cases:

Case1. Let there exists $t_2 \geq t_1$ sufficiently large, such that $x'(t) > 0$ and $(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) < 0$ for $t \geq t_2$.

Case2. Let there exists $t_2 \geq t_1$ sufficiently large, such that $x'(t) < 0$ and $(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) < 0$ for $t \geq t_2$.

Case(1). In the case we have $b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha$ is strictly decreasing for $t \geq t_2$ and there is a constant $M < 0$ such that

$$a(t) \left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)^\beta \right) < M, \quad t \geq t_2.$$

Dividing by $a(t)$ and then integrating from t_2 to t , we obtain

$$b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha \leq b(t_2)(x'(t_2))^\alpha + M^{1/\beta} \int_{t_2}^t \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} ds.$$

Letting $t \rightarrow \infty$ and using (2.1), we have $x'(t) \rightarrow -\infty$, which is a contradiction.

Next consider (2.2). Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &\geq x(t) - x(t_3) = \int_{t_3}^t b^{-1/\alpha}(s) \left(b(s)(x'(s))^\alpha \right)^{1/\alpha} ds \\ &\geq \left(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha \right)^{1/\alpha} \int_{t_3}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds, \quad t \geq t_3. \end{aligned}$$

From equation (1.1) and the last inequality, we have

$$(2.5) \quad 0 = \left(a(t)(y'(t))^\beta \right)' + q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) \geq \left(a(t)(y'(t))^\beta \right)' + q(t)y^\gamma(t)B^\gamma(t, t_3),$$

where $y(t) = b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha$. It is clear that $y(t) > 0$ and $y'(t) < 0$, and it follows that

$$-y'(t) \geq -\frac{a^{1/\beta}(t_3)y'(t_3)}{a^{1/\beta}(t)}, \quad t \geq t_3.$$

Integrating the last inequality from t to ∞ from t to ∞ , we obtain

$$(2.6) \quad y(t) \geq K_1 A_2(t), \quad t \geq t_4 \geq t_3,$$

where $K_1 = -a^{1/\beta}(t_3)y'(t_3) > 0$. Integrating (2.5) from t_4 to t and using (2.6), we obtain

$$\int_{t_4}^t q(s) K_1^\gamma A_2^\gamma(s) B^\gamma(s, t_3) ds \leq a(t_4) (y'(t_4))^\beta - a(t) (y'(t))^\beta,$$

or

$$\left(\frac{K_1^\gamma}{a(t)} \int_{t_4}^t q(s) A_2^\gamma(s) B^\gamma(s, t_3) ds \right)^{1/\beta} \leq -y'(t).$$

Again integrating from t_4 to ∞ , we get

$$K_1^{\gamma/\beta} \int_{t_4}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{a(t)} \int_{t_4}^t q(s) A_2^\gamma(s) B^\gamma(s, t_3) ds \right)^{1/\beta} dt \leq y(t_4) < \infty$$

which contradicts (2.2).

Case(2). In this case, we have

$$b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha \leq b(t_2)(x'(t_2))^\alpha = K < 0.$$

Dividing the above inequality by $b(t)$ and integrating from t_2 to t , we obtain

$$x(t) \leq x(t_2) + K^{1/\alpha} \int_{t_2}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds.$$

Letting $t \rightarrow \infty$, then condition (2.3) implies that $x(t) \rightarrow -\infty$, which is a contradiction. Next, assume condition (2.4) is satisfied. One can choose $t_3 \geq t_2$ with $\sigma(t) \geq t_2$ for all $t \geq t_3$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} x(\sigma(t)) &\geq -\left(b_1(\sigma(t))(x'(\sigma(t)))^\alpha\right)^{1/\alpha} A_1(\sigma(t)) \\ &\geq K_2 A_1(\sigma(t)), \quad t \geq t_3, \end{aligned}$$

where $K_2 = -\left(b_1(\sigma(t))(x'(\sigma(t)))^\alpha\right)^{1/\alpha} > 0$. Then from equation (1.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(a(t)\left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha)\right)^\beta\right) &= -q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) \\ &= -q(t)x^\gamma(\sigma(t)) \\ &\leq -Lq(t)A_1^\gamma(\sigma(t)), \end{aligned}$$

where $L = K_2^\gamma$. Integrating the last inequality from t_3 to t , we obtain

$$\left(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha\right) \leq L^{1/\beta} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} \left(\int_{t_3}^t q(s) A_1^\gamma(\sigma(s)) ds\right)^{1/\beta}.$$

Again integrating the above integrating from t_3 to t , we get

$$x'(t) \leq K b^{-1/\alpha}(t) \left(\int_{t_3}^t \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_{t_3}^s q(u) A_1^\gamma(\sigma(u)) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha},$$

where $K = L^{1/\alpha\beta}$. Once again integrating the last inequality from t_3 to t , we obtain

$$K \int_{t_3}^t \left(\frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_3}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} \left(\int_{t_3}^u q(v) A_1^\gamma(\sigma(v)) dv \right)^{1/\beta} du \right)^{1/\alpha} \right) ds \leq x(t_3) < \infty$$

Letting $t \rightarrow \infty$ in the above inequality, we obtain a contradiction with (2.4). Thus, we have $(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) > 0$ for $t \geq t_1$ and hence $x'(t) > 0$ or $x'(t) < 0$ for $t \geq t_1$. Then proof is now complete.

Lemma 2.2 Let conditions (C_1) and (C_2) be hold. Let $x(t)$ be an eventually positive solution of equation (1.1) for all $t \geq t_0$ and suppose that Case(II) of Lemma 2.1 holds. If

$$(2.7) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_t^{\infty} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\infty} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha} dt = \infty$$

then $x(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. Let $x(t)$ be a positive solution of equation (1.1) and there is a $t_1 \geq t_0$ such that $x(\sigma(t)) > 0$ for $t \geq t_1$. Since $x(t)$ is decreasing, we get $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x(t) = \ell \geq 0$. Assume $\ell > 0$, then $x(\sigma(t)) \geq \ell$ for all $t \geq t_2 \geq t_1$. Integrating equation (1.1) from t to ∞ , we find

$$a(t) \left(b(t) (x'(t))^\alpha \right)^\beta \geq \int_t^{\infty} q(s) \max_{[\sigma(s), s]} x^\gamma(u) ds \geq \int_t^{\infty} q(s) x^\gamma(\sigma(s)) ds.$$

Since $x(t)$ is decreasing. Dividing the last inequality by $a(t)$ and then integrating from t to ∞ , we get

$$-x'(t) \geq \frac{\ell^{1/\alpha\beta}}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left[\int_t^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{a(s)} \int_s^{\infty} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right]^{1/\alpha}.$$

Again integrating from t_2 to ∞ , we see that

$$x(t_2) \geq \ell^{1/\alpha\beta} \int_{t_2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left[\int_t^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{a(s)} \int_s^{\infty} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right]^{1/\alpha} dt.$$

which is a contradiction with (2.7). Thus $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x(t) = 0$. The proof is now complete.

Theorem 2.1 Let conditions $(C_1), (C_2)$ and $\sigma'(t) > 0$ be hold for all $t \geq t_0$, and there exists a differential function $\tau(t)$ such that

$$(2.8) \quad \tau'(t) \geq 0, \tau(t) > t, \text{ and } \sigma(\tau(\tau(t))) < t.$$

If both the first order delay equations

$$(2.9) \quad y'(t) + q(t) \left(\int_{t_0}^{\sigma(t)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_0}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} ds \right)^\gamma y^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\sigma(t)) = 0,$$

and

$$(2.10) \quad z'(t) + \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\int_t^{\tau(t)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha} z^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\eta(t)) = 0,$$

when $\eta(t) = \sigma(\tau(\tau(t)))$, are oscillatory, then every solution of equation (1.1) is oscillatory.

Proof. Let $x(t)$ be a nonoscillatory solution of equation (1.1). Then, without loss of generality, there is a $t_1 \geq t_0$ such that $x(t) > 0, x(\sigma(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1$. Choose $t_2 \geq t_1$ sufficiently large so that two cases of Lemma 2.1 hold.

Case(I). In this case, we have

$$b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha = b(t_2)(x'(t_2))^\alpha + \int_{t_2}^t a^{-1/\beta}(s) y^{1/\beta}(s) ds \geq y^{1/\beta}(t) \int_{t_2}^t a^{-1/\beta}(s) ds,$$

where $y(t) = a(t) \left(b(t) (x'(t))^\alpha \right)^\beta > 0$. It follows that

$$x'(t) \geq \frac{y^{1/\alpha\beta}(t)}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\frac{1}{a^{1/\alpha}(s)} ds \right)^{1/\alpha}.$$

Integrating the last inequality from t_2 to t , we get

$$x(t) \geq \int_{t_2}^t \frac{y^{1/\alpha\beta}(s)}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_2}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} ds \geq y^{1/\alpha\beta}(t) \int_{t_2}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_2}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} ds.$$

Let there exists $t_3 \geq t_2$ such that $\sigma(t) \geq t_2$ for all $t \geq t_3$, then

$$x(\sigma(t)) \geq y^{1/\alpha\beta}(\sigma(t)) \int_{t_2}^{\sigma(t)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_2}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} ds, \quad t \geq t_3.$$

From equation (1.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} -y'(t) &= q(t) \max_{[\sigma(t), t]} x^\gamma(s) = q(t)x^\gamma(t) \geq q(t)x^\gamma(\sigma(t)) \\ (2.11) \quad &\geq q(t)y^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\sigma(t)) \left(\int_{t_2}^{\sigma(t)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_2}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} ds \right). \end{aligned}$$

Integrating the above inequality from t to ∞ , we get

$$y(t) \geq \int_t^\infty q(s)y^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\sigma(s)) \left(\int_{t_2}^{\sigma(s)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(v)} \left(\int_{t_2}^v \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} dv \right)^\gamma ds.$$

The function $y(t)$ is clearly strictly decreasing and hence by Theorem 1 of [8] there exists a positive solution of equation (2.9) which contradicts that the equation (2.9) is oscillatory.

Case(II). Integrating equation (1.1) from t to $\tau(t)$, we obtain

$$a(t) \left((b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) \right)^\beta \geq \int_t^{\tau(t)} q(s) \max_{[\sigma(s), s]} x^\gamma(u) ds \geq \int_t^{\tau(t)} q(s)x^\gamma(\sigma(s)) ds.$$

From (2.8), we obtain

$$(b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha) \geq \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} x^{\gamma\beta}(\sigma(\tau(t))) \left(\int_t^{\tau(t)} q(s) ds \right)^{1/\beta}.$$

Integrating again the last inequality from t to $\tau(t)$, we have

$$-b(t)(x'(t))^\alpha \geq \int_t^{\tau(t)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} x^{\gamma\beta}(\sigma(\tau(s))) \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds.$$

or

$$(2.12) \quad -x'(t) \geq \frac{x^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\eta(t))}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\int_t^{\tau(t)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha}.$$

Integrating the above inequality from t to ∞ , we obtain

$$x(t) \geq x^{\gamma\alpha\beta}(\eta(t)) \int_t^\infty \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\int_t^{\tau(t)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} q(u) du \right)^{1/\beta} ds \right)^{1/\alpha} dt.$$

In view of Theorem 1 in [8] there exists a positive solution of equation (2.10) which contradicts that equation (2.10) is oscillatory. This completes the proof.

By combining Case(I) in the proof of Theorems 2.1 with Lemma 2.2, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2 *Let conditions (2.7), (C_1) and (C_2) be hold. If the first order delay equation (2.9) is oscillatory, then every solution $x(t)$ of equation (1.1) is either oscillatory or tends to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$.*

Remark 2.1 *Let $b(t) = 1$ and $\alpha = 1$, then Theorem 2.1 and Theorem 2.2 are reduced to that of in [1, 2].*

Corollary 2.1 *Let $\frac{\gamma}{\alpha\beta} = 1$, and the hypotheses of Theorem 2.1 hold. If*

$$(2.13) \quad \liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\sigma(t)}^t q(s) \left(\int_{t_0}^{\sigma(s)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(u)} \left(\int_{t_0}^u \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(v)} dv \right)^{1/\alpha} \right)^\gamma ds > \frac{1}{e},$$

and

$$(2.14) \quad \liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\eta(t)}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} \left(\int_u^{\tau(u)} q(v) dv \right)^{1/\alpha} \right)^\gamma ds > \frac{1}{e}$$

respectively, then every solution of equation (1.1) is oscillatory.

Proof. Proceeding as in the proof of Theorem 2.1, we have (2.11) and (2.12) with $\frac{\gamma}{\alpha\beta} = 1$. By condition (2.13) and (2.14) and Theorem 2.1.1 of [6], the inequalities (2.11) and (2.12) have no positive solution which a contradiction. This completes the proof.

Corollary 2.2 *Let $0 < \frac{\gamma}{\alpha\beta} < 1$, and the hypotheses of Theorem 2.1 hold. If*

$$(2.15) \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} q(t) \left(\int_{t_0}^{\sigma(t)} \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(s)} \left(\int_{t_0}^s \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(u)} du \right)^{1/\alpha} \right)^\gamma ds dt = \infty,$$

and

$$(2.16) \quad \int_{t_0}^t \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} \left(\int_t^{\tau(t)} \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(s)} \left(\int_s^{\tau(s)} q(u) du \right)^{1/\alpha} \right)^\gamma dt = \infty,$$

then every solution of equation (1.1) is oscillatory.

Proof. Proceeding as in the proof of Theorem 2.1, we have inequalities (2.11) and (2.12) with $0 < \frac{\gamma}{\alpha\beta} < 1$. By condition (2.15) and (2.16) and Theorem 3.9.3 of [6], the inequalities (2.11) and (2.12) have no positive solution. This contradiction completes the proof.

3 Examples

In this section, we present two examples to illustrate the main results.

Example 3.1 Consider the third order differential equation

$$(3.1) \quad \left(\left(\left(t \left(\frac{1}{t^2} (x'(t))^{1/3} \right) \right)^3 \right) \right) + t \max_{[t^{1/5}, t]} x(s) = 0, \quad t \geq 1.$$

Here $a(t) = t, b(t) = \frac{1}{t^2}, \alpha = \frac{1}{3}, \beta = 3, \gamma = 1, q(t) = t$, and $\sigma(t) = t^{1/5}$. A simple calculation shows that $\sigma(t) = t^{1/5} < t, \sigma'(t) > 0$ and

$$\int_1^\infty \frac{1}{a^{1/\beta}(t)} dt = \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{t^{1/3}} dt = \infty, \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{b^{1/\alpha}(t)} dt = \int_1^\infty t^6 dt = \infty.$$

It is easy to see that all condition (2.7) holds, and equation (2.9) reduces to

$$(3.2) \quad y'(t) + t(c_1 t^{9/5} + c_2 t^{5/3} + c_3 t^{23/15} - c_4 t^{7/5})y(t^{1/5}) = 0,$$

where c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 are constants. By Theorem 2.1.1 of [6] guarantees oscillation of equation (3.2) provided that

$$\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{t^{1/5}}^t (c_1 s^{9/5} + c_2 s^{5/3} + c_3 s^{23/15} - c_4 s^{7/5}) ds = \infty > \frac{1}{e}$$

and according to Theorem 2.2 every solution of equation (3.1) is either oscillatory or tends to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Example 3.2 Consider the third order differential equation

$$(3.3) \quad (t^3(t^6 x'(t))) + t^{12} \max_{[t/2, t]} x(s) = 0, \quad t \geq 1.$$

Here $a(t) = t^3, b(t) = t^6, \alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1, \sigma(t) = \frac{t}{2}, q(t) = t^{12}$. A simple calculation shows that $\sigma(t) = \frac{t}{2} < t, \sigma'(t) > 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sigma(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{t}{2} = \infty$, and $\int_1^\infty \frac{1}{t^6} dt < \infty, \int_1^\infty \frac{1}{t^3} dt < \infty$. It is easy to see that conditions (2.2), (2.4) and (2.7) hold. Further, equation (2.9) reduces to

$$(3.4) \quad z'(t) + \frac{t^{12}(t^7 - 112t^2 + 320)}{35t^7} z(t/2) = 0.$$

By Theorem 2.1.1 of [6] guarantees of oscillation of (3.4) provided that

$$\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{t/2}^t \frac{s^5(s^7 - 112s^2 + 320)}{35} ds > \frac{1}{e}$$

and according to Theorem 2.2, every solution of equation (3.4) is either oscillatory or tends to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

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